

In: Stephanidis, C. (ed.): Proc. 10th Int'l. Conf. on Human-Computer Interaction (HCI 2003), Crete, Greece, June 22-27, 2003. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Ass. Publ., Vol. 4, pp. 602-606

Pipelined Filter Combination in Product Personalization

Volker Renneberg and Uwe M. Borghoff

Institut für Software-Technologie, Fakultät für Informatik
Universität der Bundeswehr München, Munich, Germany
{volker.renneberg,uwe.borghoff}@unibw-muenchen.de

1 Introduction

In many cases, standard of-the-shelf products—i.e., products without individual customization—do not meet all customer requirements. Therefore, for instance, the automotive industry produces vehicles with personalized characteristics. Can this customization be further improved w.r.t. production time, especially in B2P relations? Today, on-line ordering systems already store user profiles that can help to match customer requirements. Another approach is mass customization where users can select a product with discrete options (e.g., different front panel color of a stereo). In this paper, we want to go further and allow more than just discrete choices. However, users are not willing to spend hours in front of computers in order to tailor a product—even when it will then fully comply with their wishes. Obviously, we need a mechanism for a computer-supported production of user recommendations. The idea is to let the computer do most of the work in personalizing the product (Koch and Schubert, 2002), based on a sophisticated profile and filtering techniques.

1.1 Product description

We use a three-layer architecture with a *product meta-model*, a *product model* and, thirdly, a *product configuration*. The product itself is being described by the product model which contains all the necessary information about the product structure and the offered services. The product model is organized hierarchically. Primarily, a product is divided into several components where components may contain sub-components. This results in a *component tree*. However, this component tree is still not sufficient to describe all real world products. A car, for instance, may either have a gasoline engine or an electric engine. Thus, the component “engine” should look different among those choices. What is missing are so-called *attributes*. These attributes are like place holders that describe the choices a user may configure. Attributes are *typed* and may carry *value intervals* or *enumerations*. Intervals themselves may be partitioned. Model validity is assured through rules. These rules describe dependencies within the product model. For example, a user wishing a car with more speed, forces the system to switch from an electric engine to a gasoline engine while increasing the horsepower simultaneously—a simple interdependency rule! A product configuration is called *valid* if it complies with the rules of the correspondent product model. In order to further improve our system, we introduce so-called *qualities* that describe functionality of components. A quality is identified by its name. Examples are “sports car” or “family truck” with obvious implications for the default product presetting. In a nutshell, the product configuration is an instance of the product model with all necessary attributes assigned. The product meta-model describes the structure of the product model.

1.2 Recommendation

To support the user in the process of filling in data into this complex structure, recommendations are generated. It is out of scope to discuss all details of the involved GUI here. Let us focus on the following aspects instead. What do we know about a user? As said earlier, we maintain a user

profile and use it during the product configuration. Since the number of model attributes may be large, we have to reduce the number of attributes that have to be configured manually. Moreover, we have to keep the configuration valid. Not an easy task as we will see.

2 Related Work

There are already several well-known techniques that aim to generate recommendations by using a user profile (Koch, 2002; Meteren and Someren, 2000): *Collaborative* filtering, *content-based* filtering or *rule-based* filtering. In our context, filtering means a) extracting the correct information from the user profile and b) using it efficiently during the recommendation process. Collaborative filtering makes use of communities by exploring the users' common desires (Borghoff *et al.*, 2001). In product configuration this means the system mines information about previous user choices within a specific community. Later, the system suggests the most common choices if asked for a recommendation for a user belonging to that specific community. In contrast, content-based filtering heavily relies on the data inside the user profile. During the configuration process the profile information will directly be used to automatically fill the product configuration. The third approach, rule-based filtering, relies on a user profile, too. Additionally, there is a set of common rules that will use the information from the user profile and calculate some settings for the attributes. Unfortunately, our second goal, getting a good reduction of manually configurable attributes, will not be reached by just using one of those techniques. Each filtering technique is useful for a specific set of attributes only. For example in car configuration, a user may need a sportive set-up (because the user belongs to that kind of community) though s/he still needs a child's safety seat (which is just specific to that user and not to the community). Also the issue of automatically filling in attributes that are predetermined by values of other attributes will be touched by rule-based filtering only. *Hybrids* try to combine those approaches in order to make use of the advantages of more than one filtering technique. Fab (Balabanovic and Shoham, 1997) combines content-based and collaborative filtering by chaining those two modules. Other researchers such as Soboroff and Nicholas (2002) try an mathematical approach in combining different methods. Still most hybrid approaches remain static.

3 Pipeline

Our approach is dynamic. It provides a pipelined combination of filtering techniques. During the configuration recommendation process an empty configuration will be fed into the pipeline. Each filter module in the pipeline will then fill some of the attributes with values. The output will be a fully or almost fully-configured product. The number of attributes that have to be configured manually can be reduced quite drastically. A rule-based approach in the pipeline is used to fill in predetermined attribute values. The chosen approach does not need a step for mixing the several configurations because during the whole recommendation process the configuration will be accessed by exactly one module at a time. Additionally, this type of filter combination is not bound to a specific filtering technique. Technically speaking, any filter may be inserted. This also means that filters belonging to the same category (like collaborative) may fulfil slightly different tasks like configuring for special communities. All those scenarios are possible by not restricting the filter modules inside the pipeline.

3.1 Architecture

Basically the pipeline consists of a chain of one ore more filter modules, a *pipeline-configuration*. The pipeline-based communication inside the pipeline and between the filter modules does not depend on a filtering technique. The idea is to have a data package which will be piped through. The output is a rated list of product recommendations. The input to the pipeline consists of

information about 1) the used filter modules, 2) the arrangement (order) of those modules, 3) the user who wants to get a product recommendation, 4) an (optionally) empty product configuration including information about the product model it belongs to, 5) an assignment which attributes will be configured by which module, 6) special user wishes, and 7) special configuration information for each filtering method.

Ad 1) and 2): Information about the arrangement inside the pipeline basically fixes the order of modules in the pipeline. This arrangement is user and product specific. E. g. in the domain of car selling a user whose main hobby interest lies in cars and who is active member of such a community will heavily rely on the opinions of others when buying a car. In some cases, taking configurations of other people in consideration may be more important to the customer than basically relying on her user profile. The latter may not contain enough information for the configuration of a car with current features (because the last deal dates back more than a few years). Thus using collaborative filtering may be more important than content-based filtering. This fact has to be reflected in the way the product configuration is generated and thus has to influence the pipeline layout. On the other hand when buying a do-it-yourself high pressure water cleaner the opinions of friends may not be a viable solution for configuring such a product (e.g., size, pressure). It will heavily depend on the physical environment the user is living in and thus on the user profile. Here content-based filtering has to be given a higher priority than, for example, collaborative filtering. Maybe the user bought such a product a few years ago and during usage s/he found some criteria which have to be present for the next one. Those may be formulated as rules and thus the rule-based filtering approach may be the first technique which has to be applied in order to fulfil the basic demands of the user. Anyway those examples show the importance of allowing the reconfiguration of the pipeline for each user for each product configuration run. Our first approach is to ask the user and put this information into the user profile. The next step will be to make use of product categorization and the hobbies of a user in order to automatically generate such a configuration.

Ad 3): Obviously the information what user wants to get a product recommendation will be needed. This information will be the key to access the user profile. Right now the user profile does not have access restrictions. By the time this will be implemented. An additional information like an access token has to be provided to the pipeline.

Ad 4): Very important are the product model and the product configuration. The product model is connected to the product configuration implicitly. It is needed because it contains important information about the possible components, their attributes including their value ranges, and, finally, the rule set describing dependencies inside the product configuration.

Our first goal is to fill an empty product configuration which will be presented as a first guess to the user. S/he will be encouraged to adjust the values to their convenience. But still the system is also designed for user interaction during configuration and thus it would be feasible to allow the user to request partial configurations. So partially filled configurations will have to be allowed, too. Additional information which may be needed to facilitate such a behavior are pointers to the components and attributes the system has to process.

Ad 5): The most difficult part in using a pipeline for product configuration is the assignment of attributes to the correct filter module. Again this information is specific for each user and product.

Ad 6) and 7): For each configuration it must be possible for the customer to declare special wishes. Normally special wishes are information not contained in the user profile or contradictory to it. This option lets the user or system adjust the behavior of the filter modules according to current needs. Imagine the user wants to try something out or intends to do a one time change to his/her personal needs. It would not be feasible to go back to the user profile and change the information before configuration and change it back afterwards.

This information on special wishes may be even more specific when concentrating on additional information for specific filter modules. Though this is not really what we want because actually it

is not supposed to be the user's task to build up a filtering algorithm that is conform to the user profile. The system itself has to do this job.

To ensure the validity a validator module is introduced that operates on the basis of the product model rules. We have to distinguish three cases: Firstly, the product configuration obeys the rules exactly. Nothing has to be done. Secondly, the product configuration contradicts those rules. The easy way is to drop such a configuration. Still it is possible to trace back to which module set the conflicting attributes and undo those changes. However, this requires a logging mechanism. The third possibility is that the product configuration is semi-valid. This means that the value ranges for some attributes are too wide and have to be narrowed. This process will be done automatically in order to avoid invalid configurations after the next step.

Finally there is the problem of evaluating configurations. The idea is to get a ranked list of product configurations at the end of the pipeline. Issues arising from ranking are: Which is the "best" configuration and how to compare a given configuration against it? How does the system handle incomplete configurations?

3.2 Example

Let our product model describe a simple car with its (sub-)components (underlined) and their attributes (italic):

The two sub-components Manual Gear Handles and Automatic Gear Handles are optional. In order to illustrate the rules of a product model we will introduce those:

1. If Car.Security-System = "electronic" then Car.Fuel Tank.Filler-Plug-Lock = "electronic".
2. If Car.Engine.Power ≥ 122 KWh then Car.Gears.Count ≥ 6.
3. Car.Gears.Type = "auto" ⇔ Car.Interior must contain the component Automatic Gear Handles and not the other one.

The user profile says about the user that she is car-addicted and member of several automotive-clubs. This leads to the conclusion that she has contact to people who have bought a similar car in the past and may give a good resource on how to configure her new car. Thus, we assume most of the attributes will be configured by a collaborative filter and, therefore, this module has to be given precedence over the others. The second entity in the pipeline will be a content-based filter for adjusting the product configuration to her special needs. And last but not least we have to add a validator checking whether the generated product configuration satisfies all product model rules. So the pipeline layout might look like this:

The configuration of the connection of the attributes to the pipeline modules is the following:

- Collaborative filtering: *Car.Engine*, *Car.Interior*, *Car.Security-System*
- Content-Based filtering: *Car.Color*, *Car.Interior.Child-Safety-Seat*
- Validator (\cong rule-based filtering): *Car.Fuel Tank*, *Car.Gears.Count*

With this information (product model including rule set, the pipeline configuration, the attribute-module assignment) an exemplary (also simplified) configuration process could look like:

First step: The collaborative filter searches for friends or people in the user's community who bought this car. This will give a certain number of configurations and attributes.

Second step: The partially filled product configuration will now be fed into the content-based filtering module. First it will detect that the customer has a small child and thus needs a child's safety seat. Beyond this fact the user also mined into her profile that she likes blue cars. This information will be used to set the color to some kind of blue.

Third step: The validator takes the product configuration which comes from the content-based filter and checks whether all rules are satisfied and whether there are free attributes which may be configured automatically. The first rule (provided that the security-system has been set to "electronic") will set the filler plug lock to "electronic". The second rule will reduce the gear count which the user will have to choose from. And the last rule will check, whether (in the collaborative filter) the correct module for the gear handles in the interior has been set.

The result is a (partially) configured product that is presented to the user. She now has to set those attributes which have not been configured so far by any filter module.

Admittedly, our simple example still has some drawbacks: First we do not present how special wishes of a user or special configurations for some filter module may be included. Secondly, there is always exactly one configuration which will be filled with values. In our example, the filter modules do not branch a single configuration into two or more. Thirdly, because the pipeline generates only one configuration it does not have to evaluate it. We also ignored contradictory value settings of attributes because we assumed that all the attributes are configured by exactly one module of the pipeline.

4 Conclusion and Future Work

We presented a technique to generate product configurations through the combination of different filtering techniques. Our hybrid approach constructs a pipeline that will eventually support loops and parallelism. This work has been done in cooperation with a team at the Technical University, Munich, Germany. We would like to especially thank Michael Koch, Martin Lacher, Thomas Leckner, and Rosemary Stegman for their time and the fruitful discussions we had.

References

- Balabanovic, M., Shoham, Y. (1997): FAB: Content-Based, Collaborative Recommendation. *CACM* **40**:3, pp. 66-72.
- Borghoff, U. M., Koch, M., Lacher, M. S., Schlichter, J. H., Weißer, K. (2001): Informationsmanagement und Communities. *Informatik Forsch. Entw.* **16**, pp. 103-109.
- Koch, M. (2002): Globale Benutzerprofile und kundenindividuelle Produkte. Proc. 4th Wirtschaftsinformatik-Symp., Vaduz, Liechtenstein, June 2002, Teubner-Verlag.
- Koch, M., Schubert, P. (2002): Personalization and Community Communication for Customer Support. Proc. WWDU 2002.
- Meteren, R. van, Someren, M. van (2000): Using Content-Based Filtering for Recommendation.
- Soboroff, I. M., Nicholas, C. K. (2002): Related, but not Relevant: Content-Based Collaborative Filtering in TREC-8. *Information Retrieval* **5**:2-3, pp. 189-208.